

Oxyfuel-combustion of RDF: Retrofit of a 440 kW_{th} grate furnace and pilot trials

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1. Motivation

- Incineration of municipal solid waste could be included in the European Emissions Trading System (EU-ETS) from 2028
- The emissions are unavoidable and have a fossil and biological origin in a 50/50 ratio
- CO₂ rich flue gas as source for carbon capture technologies

2. Plant description

- Nominal power: 440 kW
- Horizontal grate
- Automatic fuel supply & ash disposal
- 3 separately controlled primary air zones under the grate
- 2 separately controlled grate zones
- FTIR measurement of the flue gas composition

Schematic diagram of the converted grate furnace

3. Upgrade steps

Oxygen-supply

- 3 Air compressors: 898 m³/h total air outlet
- Pressure-swing adsorption: 62.5 m³/h O₂-outlet (95 % purity)
- Addition to the different primary air zones to control each separately

Condensation-stage

- Spray condenser followed by a column
- Medium: 200 kg/h water for cooling
NaOH for neutralization
- Opportunity to extract samples of the condensate

Flue gas recirculation

- Behind the condensation stage
- Pipe heating to prevent corrosive condensation
- Up to 400 m³/h recirculated condensed CO₂ rich flue gas
- Side channel blower

4. Pilot trials

The trials are part of the OxyWaste project.

Planned are three pilot trials, one with air and two in oxyfuel-mode

- Feedstock: Refuse derived fuel (RDF) approx. 75 % plastics & 25 % paper
- Heating up the plant with woodchips and air
- Transition to the oxyfuel-mode and approaching various test points
- Variable parameters.
 - O₂-concentration in the oxidizer: 21 – 27 vol. %
 - Total Lambda: 1.4 – 1.8
 - Variation of O₂-concentration in the three primary zones

Results of the design calculations for different air-leakage ratios

Converted grate furnace

Oxygen-generator

RDF-pellets

Elemental analysis [1]

Moisture [%]	Ash [% dm]	C [% dm]	H [% dm]	N [% dm]	O [% dm]	S [% dm]	Cl [% dm]	F [% dm]
5.2	8.0	55.2	6.8	3.0	26.3	0.008	0.6	0.004

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